

EXPLORING THE NUTRITIONAL POTENTIAL AND CULINARY APPLICATIONS OF PACO (*DIPLAZIUM ESCULENTUM*): A DIETARY SUPPLEMENT IN PANCAKE PREPARATION

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ABSTRACT

The researchers used Sensory Evaluation or analysis tools to determine the acceptability of a product developed. The study determined the acceptability of Paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes using its appearance, odor, taste, texture, and overall acceptability which was measured using Frequency Count weighted Mean and interpreted with the use of a 9-Point, Hedonic Scale. Appearance has a total frequency count of 307, with a mean of 8.77 points which is interpreted as Like Very Much, Odor, on the other hand, has a total frequency count of 303, with a mean of 8.66 points which is interpreted also as Like Very Much, Taste has a frequency count of 313, with a mean of 8.94 which interpreted as Like Very Much while, Texture has a frequency count of 302 with the mean of 8.62 which is interpreted as Like Very Much and the overall acceptability of the product frequency count has 306 with a mean of 8.75 which is also interpreted as Like Very Much the product. The result concluded that the developed paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes was accepted by the majority of the respondents and marketable.

Key words: *Paco (Diplazium esculentum), Dietary supplement, Pan Cake, 9-Point Hedonic Scale, Frequency Count mean*

INTRODUCTION

Snacks are common among the consumer in a variety of forms. Is available in the market are mostly high in sugar, calories, and salt as preservatives but low in nutrient content. The consumption of junk foods around the world is increasing (Shukri and Mohd Noor, 2017). Healthy snacks have been defined as items that feature a lot of foods that have beneficial effects on human health and usually have an adequate amount of nutrients. Developing dietary trends drive food producers and researchers into looking for creative goods that are not only ready for consumption immediately, but also unique in terms of nutritional value and additive content (Ciużyńska et al., 2019). A variety of health issues, including obesity, dental caries, and chronic illnesses, can affect children and adolescents whose diets were high in unhealthy snacking. Additionally, eating these snacks during adolescence and childhood increases the possibility that they may experience health issues later in life such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and cardiovascular diseases (Scholten et al., 2014). Fast food and other calorie-dense, unhealthy food options have seen a rise in popularity as a result of changing lifestyles and economic expansion.

An area's economy and civilization have been greatly influenced by the native plants there. For food, complementary medicine, and cosmetics, the Filipino people still rely on these plants. Even though many of the native species have been utilized by the local population, not enough has been researched about many of them. Paco is one of the fern indigenous vegetables that Filipinos love to eat. This vegetable which has a scientific name of *Diplazium esculentum* is usually eaten as a salad or as a side dish to a main viand. Aside from its distinctive taste, Paco is very well known to be healthy among Filipinos. It has many potential positive impacts on human health and flavors, edible Paco as a vegetable, Paco leaves are rich in fiber, making it a perfectly healthy diet for people who intends to lose weight, have heart problems, and even those with diabetes. Fiber takes time to digest thereby allowing people to feel full and lose the craving to eat. One of the top mineral contents of Paco is calcium and iron. "Pako "is classified as a green leafy vegetable, this fern variety help relieve known Vitamin B deficiencies (Atbp, 2016). It is used traditionally for the prevention or treatment of several diseases such as diabetes, smallpox, asthma, diarrhea, rheumatism, dysentery, headache, fever, wounds, pain, measles, hypertension, constipation, oligospermia, bone fracture, and glandular swellings (Semwal, et. al., 2021).

Higher unhealthy food intake in the Philippines is possibly attributable to the limited supply of nutritious food in the market and school canteen. The unavailability of nutritious food could be one of the obstacles to good eating practices especially for children and adults. Thus, it aimed to explore the nutritional potential and culinary applications of Paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a novel dietary supplement in pancake preparation. Through the sensory evaluation and to ensure that everyone might benefit from this project, especially those who need minerals and vitamins, and the residents of Brgy. Union, Dapa, Surigao del Norte, and the neighboring Barangay.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research study employed an experimental research design. The purpose of this study was to determine the acceptability of Paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as dietary supplement in pancake preparation.

Research Environment

This study was conducted at Brgy. Union, Dapa, Surigao del Norte Surigao del Norte Philippines. Barangay Union, another beautiful spot, is situated on the island of Siargao at approximately 9.7561, 126.1093. The elevation is approximately 10.5 meters or 34.4 feet above mean sea level. Union is one of the Barangay of Dapa, officially known as the Municipality of Dapa, and is a 4th class municipality in Surigao del Norte, Philippines. While most of Municipality situates on Siargao Island, it also encompasses Middle Bucas Grande and East Bucas Grande Islands.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the residents of Brgy. Union, Dapa, Surigao del Norte. A random sampling technique was used in choosing the respondents. There were 20 (57.14%) male and 15 (42.86%) female with a total of 35 (100%) served as respondents of the study conducted.

Respondents	Frequency Count	Percentage
Male	20	57.14%
Female	15	42.86%
Total	35	100%

Table 1: Respondents, Frequency Count, and Percentage

Research Instrument

It is used to determine the acceptability of the Paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as dietary supplement when preparing pan cakes. It assessed the attributes of the product in terms of its odor, taste, appearance and texture with the following criteria: It covered four attributes for evaluating the product. Each item was rated based on the different levels: Like Extremely (9) Like Very Much (8) Like Moderately (7) Like Slightly (6), neither

like nor Dislike (5), Dislike Moderately (3) Dislike Very Much (2), Dislike Extremely (1) Peryam and Pilgrim (1957).

Materials and Methods in the Production of the Recipe

Procurement of Stocks/Ingredients

The ingredients used are Paco, flour, honey, baking powder, salt, milk, egg, oil, and butter.

Utensils to be used:

The materials utilized are a nonstick pan, griddle, spatula, whisk, mixing bowls, cast iron skillet, liquid measuring cup, dry measuring cups and spoons, pancake pen, cookie scoop, mortar and pestle or Grinder/blender.

Measurement

The measurement for cooking the Paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes are 1 cup all-purpose flour, honey, 2 teaspoons baking powder, 1/2 teaspoon salt, 1 cup milk, 2 tablespoons unsalted butter, melted, or vegetable oil, 1 large egg, 1 tablespoon vegetable oil and 10 stalks with leaves (soft part) of paco need to grind/blend.

Procedures

In cooking the Paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) is used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes step 1, Preheat the nonstick pan. In a small bowl, whisk together flour, sugar, baking powder, and salt; set aside. Step 2, in a medium bowl, whisk together milk, butter (or oil), and egg. Add dry ingredients to the milk mixture; whisk until just moistened (do not over-mix; a few small lumps are fine). Step 3, Heat a large skillet (non-stick or cast-iron) or griddle over medium. Fold a sheet of paper towel in half, and moisten it with oil; carefully rub the skillet with an oiled paper towel. Step 4, for each pancake, spoon 2 to 3 tablespoons to spread batter into a round (should be able to fit 2 to 3 in a large skillet). Step 5, cook until the surface of the pancakes has some bubbles and a few have burst, 1 to 2 minutes. Flip carefully with a thin spatula, and cook until browned on the underside, 1 to 2 minutes more. Transfer to a baking sheet or platter; cover loosely with aluminum foil to keep it warm. Continue with more oil and the remaining batter. (You'll have 12 to 15 pancakes.) Serve warm, with desired toppings.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers sent a formal request to the Barangay asking permission to conduct a survey of the selected individual in Barangay Union on the acceptability of Paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes. Upon approval, the researcher distributed the scorecard.

Data Analysis

The analysis and interpretation of data were done as discussed below:

Frequency count and percentage. This was used in presenting data that specifies the percentage of paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes perceived by the respondents in terms of, taste, odor, appearance, and texture of the product.

Weighted mean. It was used in presenting the general acceptability of paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes as to its taste, odor, texture, appearance, and acceptability of the product.

ROI- Return on Investment or ROI was a profitability measure that evaluates the performance of a business by multiplying net profit by net worth. This was used in determining the net profit, gross sales, and production cost of paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes.

Results and Discussion

The Acceptability of paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes in terms of Appearance, Odor, Taste, Texture, and overall acceptability which was measured using a Frequency Count, weighted Mean, and interpreted with the use of 9-Point Hedonic Scale.

Attributes	Frequency Count	Mean	Interpretation
Appearance	307	8.77	Like Very Much
Odor	303	8.66	Like Very Much
Taste	313	8.94	Like Very Much
Texture	302	8.62	Like Very Much

Overall Acceptability	306	8.75	Like Very Much
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Table 2. Paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) is used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes.

As shown in Table 2 with the use of 9- Point Hedonic Scale, Appearance has a total frequency count of 307, with a mean of 8.77 points which is interpreted as Like Very Much, Odor, on the other hand, has a total frequency count of 303, with a mean of 8.8.66 point which is interpreted also as Like Very Much, Taste has a frequency count of 313, with a mean of 8.94 which interpreted as Like Very Much while, Texture has a frequency count of 302 with the mean of 8.75 which is interpreted as Like Very Much and the overall acceptability of the product frequency count has 306 with a mean of 8.75 which is also interpreted as Like Very Much the product.

Sensory experience plays a role in the formation of cravings and the elicitation of appetite responses only during consumption. The chemical senses, smell, taste, oral touch and irritation, and experience in the oral cavity as food is masticated and swallowed, give the overall experience commonly referred to as taste (Ohla, 2015).

Return of Investment (ROI)

It is shown in Table 3 that the ROI (Return on Investment) Computation of paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes of the production cost 195.00 pesos to produce 35 packs of paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes which can be sold at a price of 8.00 pesos each which can generate with a total gross sale of 280 pesos. Deducting the cost of production from the gross sales results in a net profit of 85.00 pesos with a total computation of ROI of 43.59%.

Product	Production Cost	Number of Pancakes	Price Each	Gross Sale	Net Profit	ROI %
Paco (<i>Diplazium esculentum</i>) is used as a dietary suppleme	195	35	8	280	85	43.59%

nt when preparing pancakes						
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Table 3. Return of Investment (ROI)

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study with the use of the 9-Point Hedonic Scale it revealed that Taste, Appearance, Texture, and Odor are important factors in the acceptability of a certain product. Thus, the paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes was accepted by the majority of the respondents.

It was found that the paco (*Diplazium esculentum*) used as a dietary supplement when preparing pancakes has an ROI or Return of investment of 43.59%, the product generates profit for production and commercialization.

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that they complied with obtaining informed consent, the respondents' were informed of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents were maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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